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Abstract: This Deliverable provides a guide on setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments (TREs) based on the experiences of setting up such a connection between the UKDS SecureLab and the Secure Data Centre at GESIS. It is designed to aid future setups of remote connections between TREs, a need which increasingly arises in the fast-changing secure data landscape, and a necessary step to improving the international data infrastructure to facilitate evidence based, global policy relevant research.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
UK Data Service/ UKDA, University of Essex	Beate Lichtwardt	blicht@essex.ac.uk
UK Data Service/ UKDA, University of Essex	Matthew Woollard	matthew@essex.ac.uk
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	Deborah Wiltshire	Deborah.Wiltshire@gesis.org
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	Libby Bishop	ElizabethLea.Bishop@gesis.org

Executive Summary

This report provides a guide on setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments (TREs)¹. It is based on the experiences of setting up such a connection between the UKDS SecureLab and other TREs, and most recently and specifically between the UKDS SecureLab and the Secure Data Centre at GESIS within the SSHOC project, WP5.4. It is designed to aid future setups of remote connections between TREs, a need which increasingly arises in the fast-changing secure data landscape, and a necessary step to improving the international data infrastructure to facilitate evidence-based, global, policy-relevant, impactful research.

As a result of the collaborative work undertaken within the SSHOC Deliverable D5.11, for the first time, controlled² GESIS data will be made available to researchers outside of Germany, via the GESIS access point at the UK Data Service Safe Room at the UKDA, University of Essex. Further, researchers will be able to access selected UKDS SecureLab data through GESIS' Secure Data Center Safe Room in Cologne.

Setting up a Secure Remote Connection between the UKDS SecureLab and the Secure Data Centre at GESIS within the SSHOC project faced considerable challenges due to the onset of the COVID-19 Pandemic in 2020 and its implications for the next two years. However, the goals of this deliverable were achieved in the end. Further, a staggered return to the offices and Safe Room openings are in sight and so, even though the SSHOC project itself comes to an end, work on and around the access points, generating use cases, improving workflows etc. will continue.

The report describes the different areas of work, tasks, and aspects that have to be addressed and taken into consideration ahead of and during the setting up of a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs. It is anticipated that this report will provide a blueprint for setting up further remote connections. The details might differ from case to case, but the steps described here are fundamental and must be addressed when setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs.

¹ Increasingly, personal/confidential, and sensitive data are made available through Secure Data Facilities which can be also referred to as Secure Access Facilities/ Secure Research Facilities/ Safe Settings/ or Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Examples for these are a) Research Data Centres (RDCs), e.g., the IAB FDZ, RDC LifBi, RDC SOEP, b) Datalabs, such as the UKDS SecureLab, HMRC Datalab, ONS SRS, Justice Data Lab etc., and c) Data Safe Havens, to name just a few.

² The terms 'controlled data' and 'secure data' (Secure Use File data) are used interchangeably in this report.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BStatG	Bundesstatistikgesetz (Federal Statistics Act)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
HP	Hewlett Packard
IAB FDZ	Forschungsdatenzentrum (FDZ) der Bundesagentur für Arbeit (BA) im Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung (IAB) (Federal Employment Agency at the Institute of Employment Research)
ONS	Office for National Statistics
RDC	Research Data Centre
SDC	Statistical Disclosure Control
SGB	Sozialgesetzbuch (German Social Code)
SRT	Safe Researcher Training
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UKDA	UK Data Archive
UKDS	UK Data Service (service provider in the UK – lead by UKDA)

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1. Introduction

A secure method of accessing confidential microdata for research purposes is via a secure remote desktop connection accessed through a Safe Room. In addition to a number of technical controls, the Safe Room provides additional physical controls (e.g., control of Safe Room access and monitoring by Safe Room staff). Essentially, the Safe Room can be thought of as a physical secured room to protect the access device.

This approach offers the infrastructure required for setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs to allow access to confidential microdata. Datasets remain on the secure servers of the data provider (in location A), which are then accessed through a secure encrypted internet connection (from location B). Only screen updates, mouse and keyboard changes are transferred through the encrypted internet connection. Therefore, no physical transfer of the confidential/sensitive dataset ever occurs; all browsing, and analysis of data are undertaken remotely from location B, on the secure servers that are based in location A.

It requires the collaboration of a minimum of two partner institutions. Party A assumes responsibility for the research data and Party B assumes responsibility for the access point. The research data resides and remains in the location of Party A, and a contract has to be agreed and signed between Party A and the User. Party B agrees to monitor the Safe Room setting and fulfils the required arrangements for permitting Users to access the data, for which a contract is required between Party A and Party B. The responsibilities, tasks and workflows required are fixed in a contract. In addition, knowledge about and trust in the partners' procedures are required.

Attempts to enable international access to controlled data have been ongoing for some time with compromises being found in allowing on-site Safe Room access to secure data for international researchers who are not based in the country of the TRE. However, this requires researchers to travel to the country of the TRE, posing considerable hurdles in terms of travel and subsistence costs, and time commitment, which are often not feasible for many researchers.

Further, there were a few initiatives³ to enable Safe Room Remote Desktop Access in order to reduce travel needs and facilitate access to data across borders. In this way, researchers could visit a Safe Room in one country to remotely access sensitive data from a Secure Data Facility in another country.

The SSHOC project represents another real step forward in this endeavour through the setting up of a Safe Room Remote Desktop Connection between the Secure Data Center at GESIS, Germany, and the UKDS SecureLab. For the first time, researchers will be able to access secure data made available by

³ One example for this is the International Data Access Network (IDAN).

GESIS abroad, via the UK Data Service Safe Room at the UKDA. Further, researchers will be able to access selected UKDS SecureLab data through GESIS' Secure Data Center Safe Room in Cologne.

Setting up such a remote access connection involves many considerations including legal, technical, procedural requirements. This report provides a guide on setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments. It is based on the experiences of setting up connections between the UKDS SecureLab and other TRE's, and most recently and specifically between the UKDS SecureLab and the Secure Data Centre at GESIS within the SSHOC project.

This work is designed to aid future setups of remote connections between TREs, a need which increasingly arises in the fast-changing secure data landscape, and a necessary step to improve the international data infrastructure to facilitate evidence-based, global, policy-relevant, impactful research. Historically, in the UK, controlled data have been made available only to UK based researchers for a number of reasons including technical requirements, Data Protection Legislation, and, not least, reluctance of data depositors to allow access outside of the UK. However, the research community outside the UK has shown an interest in accessing Controlled Data either via direct enquiries or at European events. Similarly, the Secure Data Center at GESIS regularly receives visitors interested in its secure data from across the world, who face travelling long distances to access data, until now only available within Germany.

Setting up the Secure Remote Connection between the UKDS SecureLab and The Secure Data Centre at GESIS within the SSHOC project faced some challenges. Unforeseeable and unprecedented challenges came up due to the onset of the COVID-19 Pandemic in 2020. As a result, both Safe Rooms were closed in March 2020, and staff and researchers moved to working from home. Due to the long duration of the pandemic, the Safe Rooms remain closed throughout the life of the SSHOC project. This has caused considerable, lengthy, and repeated delays at all stages of the set up and testing of the remote connection including setting available dates for technical setup and testing, providing external researchers access to Safe Rooms, and staff absences because of COVID-19 sickness and isolation rules. This had a profound impact on the timeframe of this deliverable and what could be achieved by the end of the SSHOC project. However, a staggered return to the offices and Safe Room openings are in sight and so, even though the SSHOC project itself comes to an end, work on and around the access points, generating use cases, improving workflows etc. will continue.

The report comments on the main areas of work/tasks, and different aspects that have to be taken into consideration ahead of and during the endeavour of setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs and, thus, provides guidance for the necessary steps along the way. The details may be different in each case, but this report should provide a useful blueprint for setting up future Secure Remote Connection between two TREs.

2. Framework for Access to Confidential Data⁴

Before the main steps necessary when implementing a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments are described, general thoughts need to be dedicated to the overarching framework for access to secure microdata.

2.1 Conceptual Framework for Access to Confidential Data

All access to personal data is managed at a European level by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and at a national level through legislation.

The ‘Five Safes’ Framework,⁵ pioneered by the UK’s Office for National Statistics and implemented as part of the UK Data Service’s SecureLab system, provides a conceptual basis for the implementation of risk management against the disclosure of personal data and thus the maintenance of the confidentiality of that type of data. The Framework is in use across the globe and, while there are multiple differences in terms of its specific interpretation, the underpinning principles remain the same.

For international collaborations on accessing controlled data across borders an additional concept, that of *equivalence*, is needed to deal with some of the differences between the national implementations of data protection. There is no guarantee that our implementation of equivalence will be valid in any bilateral agreement between a data controller and a data service provider. However, the conceptual agreement works in principle between the UK and Germany, and between Germany and the UK.

Access facilities (Research Data Centres, Secure Labs, Safe Data Havens, etc.) exist to provide secure access to confidential or confidential data (usually, but not exclusively, microdata) for research purposes. Providing secure access to confidential microdata is predicated on compliance with data and privacy protection regulations, and the implementation of best practices to minimise the disclosure risk. These data are typified as information which could be used to identify (legal) individuals/data subjects (persons or institutions).

There are different methods of protecting confidential data so that they can be used for research purposes while mitigating the risk of disclosure of personal information. Here it is considered using international secure remote desktop access via a Safe Room. This approach offers a safe environment to

⁴ This section is based on the SSHOC D5.9 (Woollard et al. 2021), which can be referred to for more information.

⁵ See Desai, Ritchie, and Welpton 2016

access the confidential data. Datasets remain on the secure servers of the data provider (in location A), which are then accessed via a secure encrypted internet connection (from location B). No physical transfer of the confidential data ever occurs. All browsing and analysis of data are undertaken remotely from location B, on the secure servers which are based at location A. The Safe Room at location B provides additional physical controls (e.g., control of Safe Room access and monitoring by Safe Room staff). This element of the ‘safe environment’ element of the Five Safes framework can be made more or less ‘safe’ by the inclusion of additional controls (which may be a deterrent or a control for monitoring (or both).)

To improve the international research infrastructure and, thus, aid researchers requiring access to international confidential microdata to be able to access these data within their countries, without travelling abroad, a boilerplate contract between two parties was provided, whereby each party represents a mature data service with its own Research Data Centre (RDC) in a different country⁶. This boilerplate contract is based on an existing contract between the RDC of the Federal Employment Agency at the Institute of Employment Research (IAB FDZ), Nuremberg, Germany and the UK Data Service at the UK Data Archive, University of Essex. It provides a template for future research agreements and can be easily adapted to other institutions planning to facilitate access to their confidential microdata via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access. Variations of this contract are in use for multiple access points across Europe and worldwide, proving the value of this contract. A full description of both the Framework and the boilerplate contract can be found in the SSHOC D5.9 report ‘Framework and contract for international data use agreements on remote access to confidential data’.⁷

Four important areas to note are that the contract:

1. is predicated on mature (or at the very least) existing ‘secure access’ arrangements at both parties.
2. will need to be adapted accordingly to the varying legal, institutional, and technical requirements of both parties, which can differ considerably between institutions and countries.
3. may also need to alter some specific terminology to make it more appropriate for local requirements.
4. is in English, but it could be translated.

For these reasons, recommendation is to use of unilateral agreements.

Almost all the clauses within the contract relate explicitly or implicitly to the Five Safes framework. The following paragraphs explain each of the Five Safes in a short definition. This is followed by all of the relevant references within the contract, i.e., those which deal with the specific issue. It should be clear

⁶ Woollard et al. 2021

⁷ Woollard et al. 2021

that just having a contract in place does not mean that these elements of the framework are dealt with. Specific documented procedures for each of the parties to the contract may also need to be in place.

Safe Data

Data is treated to protect any confidentiality concerns.

In principle there is a wide range of treatment which can be used to protect the confidentiality concerns in any dataset. In practice there are three broad areas. In general, complete de-identification (the removal of any names, addresses or direct identifiers) is the first. In some cases, this will not be compatible with the use of the data, but generally it will suffice. The removal of this information will not anonymise data and there will still be a risk of disclosure.

(In the agreements between UK and DE, the form of ‘safe data’ is prescribed by the German Law on Statistics for Federal Purposes and is defined as ‘faktisch anonymisierte’ (‘factually anonymised’)⁸ data. In practice it is the responsibility of the data owner (controller) to provide data at a safe (to them) level.

Safe Projects

Safe Projects can be defined in many ways. At the lowest end of the spectrum, one might use the question: is this use of data appropriate? But, given the way in which the interaction was chosen, the risk becomes not just the appropriateness of use, but more specifically whether:

Research projects are approved by data owners for the public good.

The precise steps of the project approval process are not explicitly detailed in our contracts; only that there must be a process.

The rationale here is that different organisations/countries may have different rules. The bottom line is that all projects must be approved according to the rules set down by the data controller, which must be in line with European and local law. In cases where GDPR applies, the project must be in the public interest and for the public good. However, data controllers may apply other conditions beyond these two. It is essentially the responsibility of the Data Provider to ensure that the conditions are met for each project, and that the researchers do not extend the remit of their project beyond the approved project application.

In practice also, Party A will screen any application to reduce the labour of the data controller. This screening may be just checking that all relevant information is provided and it may also be a complete review of the proposal. In the latter case it is still the data controller which is responsible for the decision.

⁸ BStatG: https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bstatg_1987/_16.html; [Accessed April 11, 2022]. See also Research Data Centres of the Statistical Offices of the Federation and the Federal States: <https://www.forschungsdatenzentrum.de/en/anonymity>; [Accessed April 11, 2022].

Safe People

Researchers are trained and authorised to use data safely.

Both parties agree to collect the information needed for researchers to be appropriately identifiable in the event of being involved in a breach. Since breach penalties may also arise at an institutional level, a researcher must be identifiable by both name and institution. Approved Users will be given personalised user credentials which also provides the method for ensuring that only a person accredited (through training) is accepted as a User.

Pre-access basic training in safe data handling is a requirement for Users. The form of training must be both generic (i.e., pertaining to safe data handling) and specific to the access methods in place at the access point. Whether or not refresher training is a requirement will be down to the practices of the access provider. Ongoing support for researchers is part of the contractual relationship.

Safe Settings

A SecureLab environment prevents unauthorised use and access to the data.

A safe setting relates to the setting or environment in which data is accessed. At its most basic form (and generally at a national level) this is the provision of a secure access facility where the User is in the same physical facility as the data. A less primitive safe setting is the provision of a desktop environment which allows Users to carry out research remotely, with the data never leaving its secure facility. Remote access of this type is now the norm. In the UK under COVID restrictions the principal data controllers accepted the additional risk of having researchers access restricted data remotely from their home workstations. In the context of this project, the primary means of implementing Safe Settings is the provision of a Secure Remote Connection between the two parties and the provision of a 'Safe Room' in both of the parties. User credentials and user project areas are detailed in the contract, but the contract does not mention whether user areas should be separate, as this will depend on the permissions from the data controller in research project applications. Best practice would ensure that issued user credentials differ for different projects.

The issue of the maintenance of Thin Clients and software is also discussed in the contracts. Essentially, the Thin Clients remain the property of Party A, and should be managed by Party A. Similarly, responsibility for the provisioning of software and its licensing is the responsibility of Party A.

Safe Outputs

Safe outputs are those which have been screened and approved as non-disclosive. No person or institution can be identified from the results of an analysis of survey or administrative data.

The contracts make it clear that Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) is undertaken by Party A (Data Provider). The specific SDC method is not specified.⁹ The understanding is that the first party applies their own method of disclosure control. They are the data processors, so have this responsibility to ensure that the outputs are correctly reviewed to prevent a breach of personal information.

There is also an expectation that the researcher understands enough about Statistical Disclosure Control to not request outputs that are obviously in breach of the rules of Party A's disclosure control. Party A is responsible for guidelines, and training of researchers regarding safe outputs, The latter should be part of the training requirement for Users.

2.2 Legislative Framework

All countries of the European Union have the EU data protection basic regulation in common. But country-specific laws can also play a role here. Thus, not only EU law but also national law applies to the implementation of data access. It depends on the data itself which national law is applicable. For example, social security data in Germany is subject to the Social Security Code or federal statistics are subject to the Federal Statistics Act. This means that for the implementation of secure data access to confidential/sensitive data, the respective national legislation must be taken into account. The legal departments must decide whether it is necessary to embed national laws in the agreement or not. For GESIS the following legislation has been taken into account:

- Datenschutz-Grundverordnung (DSGVO),
- Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (BDSG),
- Landesdatenschutzgesetze,
- Bundesstatistikgesetz (BstatG),
- General Data Protection Regulation GDPR.

Other legislation that might need to be considered by German institutions are, for example¹⁰:

- Telemediengesetz (TMG),
- Telekommunikationsgesetz (TKG),
- Datenschutzrichtlinie für elektronische Kommunikation (Richtlinie 2002/58/EG), better known as ePrivacy-Richtlinie.

⁹ Recommendation: The Statistical Disclosure Control Handbook (Griffiths et al. 2019) produced by the Safe Data Access Professionals: <https://securedatagroup.org/>; [Accessed April 11, 2022]

¹⁰ German Social Code, Section 78 Book X, Section 282 para.7 Book III, Section 35 Book I: Sozialgesetzbuch: <https://www.sozialgesetzbuch-sgb.de/>; [Accessed April 11, 2022].

For the United Kingdom, as for Germany, national legislation as well as EU legislation play a role, namely the

- Statistics and Registration Service Act, 2007¹¹.
- Digital Economy Act, 2017¹².
- Data Protection Act, 2018¹³.
- General Data Protection Regulation¹⁴.
- Privacy and Electronic Communications (EC Directive) Regulations 2003 (PECR)¹⁵
- e-Privacy Directive 2002¹⁶
- Decision on the adequate protection of personal data by the United Kingdom: Law Enforcement Directive | European Commission (europa.eu)¹⁷
- The EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement | European Commission (europa.eu)¹⁸

Post Brexit, the Decision on the adequate protection of personal data by the United Kingdom: Law Enforcement Directive¹⁹ allows the UK to have personal data transferred to it which relates to the law enforcement. Thus, it is permissible for user information to be transmitted between the EU and the UK which may be used in the event of a breach from the secure access system. Finally, the EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement²⁰ provides additional data protection adequacy provisions so forms part of the overall legal framework.

¹¹ Legislation.gov.uk.: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2007/18/contents>; [Accessed April 11, 2022c]

¹² Legislation.gov.uk.: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2017/30/contents/enacted>; [Accessed April 11, 2022b]

¹³ Legislation.gov.uk.: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/contents/enacted>; [Accessed April 11, 2022a]

¹⁴ Information Commissioner's Office: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr>; [Accessed April 11, 2022]

¹⁵ Legislation.gov.uk.: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2003/2426>; [Accessed April 11, 2022d]

¹⁶ Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 Concerning the Processing of Personal Data and the Protection of Privacy in the Electronic Communications Sector (Directive on Privacy and Electronic Communications) 2002

¹⁷ European Commission 2021b

¹⁸ European Commission 2021a

¹⁹ European Commission 2021b

²⁰ European Commission 2021a

3. Setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs

When setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments, considerations and a considerable amount of work has to be undertaken in the following five main areas: contracts, technical setup, data depositor permissions, procedures, and communication.

Figure 1: Setting up a Secure Remote Connection – Main Areas of Work/Tasks

Comments on each of these five areas will be made in the consecutive five sections.

Technical and researcher testing sessions are recommended to complete the setup, ensuring everything works as it should be. These will be briefly addressed in section 4.

3.1 Contracts

As a basis for the contract the Framework and contract for international data use agreements on remote access to confidential data has been used, a template that has been generated as part of SSHOC Task 5.4. A full discussion of the Framework is not included here, however the SSHOC D5.9 report ‘Framework and contract for international data use agreements on remote access to confidential data’ describes in detail both the Five Safes Framework which informs and underpins the development of the contract for international data use agreements and provides a template for those wishing to develop similar international data use connections and agreements.²¹

To facilitate access to the respective controlled microdata via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access, this framework and contract template was adopted and made the necessary amendments as and where required.

Almost all the clauses within the contract relate explicitly or implicitly to the Five Safes Framework. However, it should be clear that just having a contract in place, does not mean that these elements of the framework are dealt with. Specific documented procedures for each of the parties to the contract also need to be in place.

The following list contains an overview of what, in authors’ opinion, needs to be considered when setting up a contract for international data use agreements on the Provision of Safe Room Remote Desktop Access to confidential data. The full details can be found in the Template Contract.²²

A contract for international data use agreements on remote access to confidential data could consist of sections with the following contents.

- Considerations
- Definitions
- Services of Parties
- Period of Agreement and Modification/Termination
- Available Research Data and Fees
- Content of Appendix
 - General Description of Safe Room Desktop Services
 - Application Process
 - Available Research Data
 - Fees
 - Relevant Legislative Texts

²¹ Woollard et al. 2021

²² Woollard et al. 2021

Pledge in Data Secrecy Responsibility within Party B

The contract regulates remote access to factually anonymous research data involving two parties. Party A is responsible for storing the research data, while Party B is responsible for securing the access point to the research data. The contract relates to the specific procedures which are in place.

The Safe Room hosted by Party B is open to all approved Users of Party A. Party B guarantees to provide equal and non-discriminative access to the Safe Room to all approved Users of Party A, especially not to over-privileged Users affiliated with Party B.

Finally, in the Template Contract there are a number of clauses which may need to be considered in light of local practices and procedures.

3.2 Technical Setup

A secure method of accessing confidential microdata for research purposes is via a secure remote desktop connection accessed through a Safe Room.

The Safe Room provides additional physical controls (e.g., control of Safe Room access and monitoring by Safe Room staff). Essentially, the Safe Room can be thought of as a physical secured room to protect the access device.

In the following, some commentary is provided regarding the Remote Access System, Safe Rooms and Thin Clients.

3.2.1 Remote Access System

Ideally, the organisations intending to set up Safe Room Remote Desktop Access to their controlled data should have mature (i.e., long running, successful and growing) systems in place for providing remote access to confidential microdata to researchers.

Whereas the UKDS SecureLab has offered remote access to its confidential data nationally for over a decade, GESIS is only starting to set up a remote access system – nationally and internationally at the same time.

Therefore, the below figure will, as one example, illustrate the UKDS SecureLab infrastructure.

Figure 2: UKDS SecureLab infrastructure

Access is via a web-based interface that uses secure encrypted Citrix Virtual Private Network technology. Data are not downloadable; access is remotely from organisational desktop or via the UKDA Safe Room or via one of the SafePods across the UK. Outputs are subject to Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC).

3.2.2 Safe Room

A Safe Room is a secure physical environment that consists of a secure working facility in which the confidentiality of the data for research can be ensured.

A secured remote desktop connection allows researchers to work via a Thin Client (access device), that is located in a Safe Room at Party B; with the research data stored on Party A servers. The dataset never leaves the facilities of Party A; only screen updates are transmitted to the Thin Client in the Safe Room hosted by Party B.

The UKDS Safe Room at the UKDA, and the Safe Room at the Secure Data Centre at GESIS Cologne are both well-established and have been successfully used for many years. Safe Room requirements are outlined in the contract,²³ Safe Room procedures are outlined in the respective procedure documents.

²³ Woollard et al. 2021

3.2.3 Thin Clients

A Thin Client is a computer which is configured solely to connect to the Secure Data Facility servers. It does not contain accessible storage capacity and will not boot until an authorised member of staff enters a password. Once the client has booted the user will only be provided with an option for logging into their Secure Data Facility account. The user will not, for example, be able to navigate to other web pages nor use other software applications.

For remote access to the UKDS SecureLab within the UK, Thin Clients are not used. However, for international access to controlled UKDS SecureLab data the UK Data Service:

- restricts access to be only available from within a Safe Room,
- uses a Thin Client with custom locked down configurations.

This is for additional data protection and security; it also prevents modifications from being made to the Thin Client using the HP Write Filter.

There are several advantages of using a Thin Client. Thin Clients enable the data provider to lock the machine down, leaving fewer opportunities to try and circumvent the protection that is put in place. Another benefit of using Thin Clients is that they are cheaper and a lot smaller than conventional desktop machines, as the latter are designed to run applications beyond Chrome and Firefox. Thin Clients are small boxes, and sometimes can be attached to the back of a monitor. The primary purpose of the Thin Clients is to specifically connect to the remote resource, and then that remote resource does all the editing, processing, and analysing work and prevents the requirement of secure data being transferred across the network. The simplicity and manageability of Thin Clients are indeed important factors.

The UK Data Service and GESIS have opted for two different types of Thin Clients. The UK Data Service used a HP t540 Thin Client whereas GESIS used a Dell Wyse 5070 Thin Client.

The setting up of the Thin Clients

UKDS Thin Client

When starting SSHOC D5.11, the UK Data Service had already established HP Thin clients that are currently in use in Safe Rooms. They work well and are simple to maintain. One additional very important aspect is that they had been already agreed and accepted by a variety of data owners, including the ONS. For all the above reasons, the decision was made to continue to employ another HP Thin Client, this time a HP t540 Thin Client. It is Windows-based, and using the existing series of instructions, the Thin Clients were configured and signed off by the UKDS Service Security Manager for validation that the Thin Clients were locked down in a way that is safe and secure. The instructions detail how the machine is locked down, so the only operation a User (without administration rights) can perform is to log in to the UKDS

SecureLab service. Furthermore, configuration of certain settings using HP Easy Shell locks down the system limiting user operations to the minimum required.

The UKDS Thin Client is locked down into Kiosk mode, so it only launches a browser which only connects to the SecureLab Service. The User can then login and launch an available desktop. All data and processing are operated and located by the remote SecureLab service.

For the UKDS Thin Client, the IP address and Gateway, e.g., how it connects to the internet, had to be adjusted by the administrator at GESIS. This requires the partner institution to have access to control the changes on the Thin Client. This is configured like that because lots of places do not always have a permanent static address, so if it changes, the choices are to either pick one up automatically using DHCP from the local partner server or work with the local partner administrator manually configure it up.

GESIS' Thin Client

The GESIS Thin Client works differently. Making changes was straightforward. However, these changes were not permanent but could be authorised at the remote end at GESIS where the GESIS administrator used the management console to accept the changes UKDS colleagues were proposing. This has proven to be a good approach and a good way of handling it. It still meets the security requirements as all changes need to be confirmed/validated by the institution where the data are held (Party A), ensuring the Thin Client owner is still controlling the Thin Client.

Prior to the exchange of the Thin Clients, some pre-configuration was required. For this, technical information needed to be exchanged. The following extraction is an example for the information required by GESIS.

Figure 3: Information to pre-configure GESIS' Thin Client

For our Thin Client to be hosted in your Safe Room, we need the following information to pre-configure our Thin Client *before shipping* it to you. Furthermore, you need to configure your firewall and prepare the Thin Client *before a connection* can be tested. Photos referred to in the following can be found in the accompanying folder ("Photos").

1. Information for pre-configuration of our Thin Client

For connecting our Thin Client to [LAN](#) it will need a static IP-Address inside a firewall secured IPv4 network. We can accept any private static IP-Address connected to the Internet by a public SNAT-Address.

For pre-configuring our Thin [Client](#) **we need the following information**

A static IP-Address:

- IP-Address

For network configuration of the Thin Client:

- Internal private IP-Address
- Network-Mask
- Gateway-IP

For our firewall to allow IP-Connections from our Thin Client to our VDI:

- SNAT-Address

The Wyse terminal that GESIS sent to the UK Data Service, has a slightly different setup to the one received from the UKDS. It is Linux-based, it communicates out to a central location, so any settings that need to be adjusted or updated can be done in both directions.

Exchanging the Thin Clients

Shipping the Thin Clients from the UK to Germany and vice versa was quite an endeavour. This had its causes in new regulations following Brexit, and difficulties caused by delays due to the COVID-19 Pandemic situation. Parties setting up new remote access connections would be advised to consider potential shipping restrictions and explore alternatives options if this is likely to be problematic.

Further, there may be security changes that occur within institutions over time. These should be anticipated and considered. For the UK Data Service, for example, this caused some issues as the University of Essex did not have any restrictions of DNS and what DNS Service one could go to. When the GESIS Thin Client arrived, the connection did not work initially, because the DNS was locked down, specifying that an Essex DNS Server that calls remote DNS Servers was used. This issue had its root in the tightening of security and institutional protection measures, so only certain ports are allowed in and out. This was in response to an increase in viruses and hacking attempts and meant the UKDS server could not connect to the GESIS server.

Following communication between the IT departments of both partners, the reason for the failure to connect was identified and the necessary settings adjusted. A second technical testing followed to ensure successful connection was possible. Adjustments are possible. However, if tightening of security in writer locations occurs in either partner, the fewer the number of ports required, the easier it is to set up the Thin Clients.

3.3 Data Depositor Permissions

Secure Data Access Facilities have been making controlled data available to researchers within the country for many years and well-established procedures exist to ensure the safe and ethical use of these data. However, risk management nationally is slightly different to risk mitigation for international access to controlled microdata, where additional security considerations have to be made and implemented.

An important step on the way towards making controlled data available to international researchers is to get the permission of the data depositors to do so. Different data depositors have different levels of risk-averseness. In our experience, it is helpful to be able to demonstrate not only the access conditions and application procedures, but also the respective Licence Compliance Policies of the international partners to convince data depositors that risk mitigation has been taken very seriously and that the measures taken means allowing access internationally poses no higher risk than nationally.

3.3.1 UKDS SecureLab

For over a decade the UKDS has been making controlled data available remotely to UK researchers using the Fives Safes Framework and trust to handle controlled data is demonstrated through various accreditations.²⁴ As pioneers in data curation and managing long-term access to high quality data, the UK Data Service has established key contacts and long-lasting relationships with data owners.

It is only recently,²⁵ that the UKDS SecureLab has started making 43 of its controlled longitudinal datasets available to international researchers via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access at selected partner institutions (see Appendix 1). Similar to the beginnings of the SecureLab (then called Secure Data Service (SDS)) longitudinal data owners have been pioneering remote access to their controlled data, namely, ISER (Institute for Social and Economic Research) and CLS (The Centre for Longitudinal Studies) have agreed to making some of their Controlled Data available²⁶ outside of the UK. This advancement is consequential as their Safeguarded Data are already widely used by the European researcher community.

The UK Data Service has been working closely with ISER and CLS for over two decades in enabling access to their data under all access tiers. ISER is a prestigious ESRC Research Centre based at the University of Essex, and the data owner for the British Household Panel Survey and its successor, Understanding Society. The Centre for Longitudinal Studies (CLS), a renewed ESRC Research Centre, leads four UK longitudinal cohort studies: the 1958 National Child Development Study, the 1970 British Cohort Study, Next Steps and the MCS.

Building on the Fives Safes Framework, special application forms and user agreements have been designed fit for remote access from outside the UK via a partner's Safe Room. Data negotiations included information on the proposed access model, risk mitigation and user communication. Data owners were content with the measures put in place, including the user's agreement of each Compliance Policy as appropriate.

Finally, it is important to stress that only remote access UKDS SecureLab data are being made available to international researchers outside of the UK via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access in our partner institution. Safe Room access SecureLab data are not available to researchers outside of the UK.

²⁴ The ISO 27001 and DEA Processor Accreditation status process have assessed the UK Data Service as an organisation against security and capability controls required for the two standards.

²⁵ From 14 February 2022, for the first time, the UK Data Service is making selected UK controlled data available to researchers abroad. As a first step, selected SecureLab/controlled datasets from the Institute for Social and Economic Research (ISER) and the Centre for Longitudinal Studies (CLS), will become available via a Safe Room access point at one of our IDAN Partners, the Research Data Centre (FDZ) of the Federal Employment Agency (BA) at the Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany (For more information, please see UK Data Service: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/about/research-and-development/international-data-access-network-idan/>; [Accessed April 11, 2022c]).

²⁶ Please see the detailed list of all 43 datasets in Appendix 1.

3.3.2 Secure Data Centre at GESIS

GESIS makes 21 highly detailed and sensitive datasets from key German and International social surveys available for on-site use via the Secure Data Center. A full list of these datasets can be found via the data catalogue on the GESIS website²⁷. Here researchers can find detailed descriptions of the studies and useful documents such as codebooks, as well as instructions on how to apply for these data. This ensures that the information required by researchers to apply for data is easily accessible in a single location.

GESIS has a unique structure, having a number of Research Data Centers (RDCs). Those RDCs offer a special service for several survey programs for which GESIS partially participates in data collection or is permanently responsible for the data processing, archiving and delivery, work that is guided by the criteria of the German Council for Social and Economic Data (RatSWD)²⁸. This means that for secure access datasets, such as those from the ALLBUS which is managed by one of the GESIS RDCs, contracts do not need redrawing in order to facilitate sharing through the remote connection with the UKDS SecureLab. Instead, written permission is required, and is being sought currently to confirm which datasets can be made available to international researchers based in the UK.

3.4 Procedures

In this section some of the UKDS SecureLab application procedures are discussed as an example to illustrate the procedures typically in place in a TRE with an established remote access system

For international Safe Room Remote Desktop Access, some procedures have been amended.

UK Data Archive internal process/procedure documents include the following documents:

- [Research Data Handling and Security Guide for Users](#)²⁹ [CD171]
- Non Disclosure Agreement³⁰ [CD005]
- Licence Compliance Policy³¹ [CD142]
- End User Licence³² [CD137]
- ESRC Accredited researcher application [CD139_IDAN] – split into form and proposal

²⁷ Information of the secure access datasets held at the Secure Data Center at GESIS can be found via their data catalogue (GESIS:

[https://search.gesis.org/?source={%22from%22:20,%22query%22:{%22bool%22:{%22must%22:\[{%22query_string%22:{%22query%22:%22SDC%22,%22default_operator%22:%22AND%22}},%22filter%22:\[{%22term%22:{%22type%22:%22research_data%22}}\]}\]}&lang=en](https://search.gesis.org/?source={%22from%22:20,%22query%22:{%22bool%22:{%22must%22:[{%22query_string%22:{%22query%22:%22SDC%22,%22default_operator%22:%22AND%22}},%22filter%22:[{%22term%22:{%22type%22:%22research_data%22}}]}]}&lang=en); [Accessed April 12, 2022]).

²⁸ RatSWD: <http://www.ratswd.de/>; [Accessed April 12, 2022]

²⁹ UK Data Service 2021b

³⁰ UK Data Archive 2021

³¹ UK Data Service 2017

³² UK Data Service 2021a

- ESRC Accredited researcher application form³³
- ESRC Accredited researcher application proposal³⁴
- Secure Access User Agreement_IDAN³⁵ [CD140_IDAN]
- SecureLab Authorisation Process³⁶ [CD154].

In the following section the focus will be on the access condition and application process.

3.4.1 Access conditions and application processes

The application process needs to be clearly outlined and available online. The below screenshot illustrates how this could be done. The fourth box under 'Which secure data application process?' refers to international access to non-ONS data and describes how to 'Apply to access non-ONS data from outside the UK'.

Figure 4: Apply to access non-ONS data from outside UK

Source: UK Data Service: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/find-data/access-conditions/secure-application-requirements/>; [Accessed April 11, 2022a].

The Guide the link leads to contains information about the UKDS SecureLab, researcher- and system requirements for access, outlines the application process (including project application, Secure Access User Agreement, Safe Researcher Training), informs about the account setup as well as turnaround times (please see screenshot below).

³³ UK Data Service 2022a

³⁴ UK Data Service 2022b

³⁵ UK Data Service 2022c

³⁶ CD154 can be made available on request.

Figure 5: Application guidance: UKDS SecureLab: access to non-ONS data for researchers outside of the UK via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access

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Source: UK Data Service 2022e.

The application process consists of several components which fall mainly into the four following areas: project application, User Agreement, Safe Researcher Training (SRT), UKDS SecureLab account setup. If the application process was completed successfully, and the SRT passed, the Technical Support team will set up the account and provide the researcher with the UKDS SecureLab login details.

All details are provided in the linked resources. However, one area of the application process should be highlighted specifically: the Safe Researcher Training.

Safe Researcher Training

To access UKDS SecureLab data, all project team members must complete the online Safe Researcher Training (SRT) course, which covers:

- Data security and personal responsibility, including legal background, security model, breaches, and penalties,
- Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC), how to make statistical outputs safe and what SDC principles are used,
- Using the UKDS SecureLab, how to use the interface, what can be found where, how to request imports and outputs.

SRT courses are run regularly, and, as a result of the Pandemic, online. Following the SRT course participants have to pass an online test which will be marked. Passing the test is a requirement to have a project account setup and receive personal login details.

If a researcher has not logged in for more than 3 years, s/he must complete a short online MoodleX Refresher Course before being allowed to access the UKDS SecureLab again.

The above describes the situation for the UKDS SecureLab. The processes for TREs that offer access via a Safe Room only may differ slightly. For example, the application documents relevant to applications to the Secure Data Centre at GESIS differ³⁷ and a further discussion of these can be found in the Milestone Report (MS29). GESIS is in the process of developing a remote access system so its application processes and documents will undergo a review ready for this new system. Changes will include the introduction of a Safe Researcher Training as part of the application process.

As part of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project, a canonical set of training materials were developed by experts at GESIS and are available for Data Access Facilities to adapt and use for their own training needs.³⁸ The Secure Data Center, in collaboration with other TREs in Germany, are working to adapt these materials to develop a new online training course suitable for remote access systems.

³⁷ GESIS internal process/procedure documents:

- [Licence compliance policy](#) (GESIS 2021)
- [Guidelines for the Secure Data Center Safe Room](#) (GESIS 2020)
- [Usage regulations](#) (GESIS 2018a)
- [Data Use Agreement](#) (GESIS 2018b)
- [Secure handling of research data](#) (GESIS 2014).

³⁸ Wiltshire 2021

3.4.2 Booking Safe Room sessions

For accessing controlled GESIS data via the UK Data Service Safe Room, UK based researchers can book the UK Data Service Safe Room online for sessions during normal opening/office hours.

The UK Data Service provides the Safe Room and the technical infrastructure. Data access is organised via the data provider (GESIS).

To make a booking for the UKDS Safe Room at the UK Data Archive, University of Essex, UK based researchers have to complete an online form³⁹ and select 'Safe Room booking' from the dropdown list under 'Your query' -> 'What would you like to contact us about?'

Please note, at present the UKDS Safe Room at the UK Data Archive, University of Essex, is closed due to the COVID-19 Pandemic. However, there are plans to re-open the Safe Room within the coming months.

Researchers in Germany wishing to make a booking for the Secure Data Center Safe Room, will need to email the Secure Data Center via their support email (sdc@gesis.org). The Safe Room is currently closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic but will be open again in the next few weeks. Visits can be arranged for Monday to Friday, during usual office hours (09:00-16:30).

3.4.3 Safe Room procedures

UK Data Service Safe Room at the UKDA⁴⁰

The UK Data Service 'SecureLab Safe Room Access Procedures' document can be made available on request.

The Safe Room has four terminals. Three of these can, if required, be used for accessing IAB, CASD, and GESIS data. It may be possible for more than one user to share the same terminal, if working on the same project, depending on available space.

The workspaces are divided by desk partition walls, and privacy screens are in place.

A short Safe Room training must be attended, and a Non-Disclosure Agreement must be signed by the User when visiting for the first time. Online booking is a prerequisite for every visit.

Lockers are available for Users to store personal items outside of the Safe Room.

³⁹ UK Data Service: <https://beta.ukdataservice.ac.uk/help>; [Accessed April 11, 2022d]

⁴⁰ The UK Data Service Safe Room at the UKDA is located at the University of Essex, giving easy access to its many researchers and PhD students.

Users undergo an identity check and need to be signed in and out. A secure door access control is in place for the Safe Room.

Mobile phones and pen and paper are not allowed in the Safe Room. However, there are individual whiteboards available in the Safe Room, which will need to be wiped clean by the User before leaving.

The GESIS Secure Data Center Safe Room

The Safe Room is a safe data enclave situated at GESIS Institute for the Social Sciences in Köln, Germany. The Safe Room is a secure room, with four workstations that can facilitate visits by a maximum of four researchers on any single day (outside of pandemic restrictions).

Researchers are not permitted to take personal belongings into the Safe Room, including electronic devices, so lockers are provided to allow researchers to securely store their belongings during their visit. Researchers should take their belongings with them at the end of the day, even if their visit will last more than one day.

The Safe Room is a secure environment, entry to the room is controlled through a door access control system. Within GESIS, only Secure Data Center staff have an access key for the room, access by other staff such as IT personnel is facilitated by Secure Data Center staff.

Upon arriving at GESIS, researchers are greeted by Secure Data Center staff who check their identity through official sources of photographic ID, such as passport or ID card. At the Safe Room, the researcher is required to leave all their belongings in the secure lockers before entering the room. Researcher authentication is through a unique username and password supplied by the UKDS SecureLab team. The researcher is given an access fob, so they can access the room. This access fob is returned to Secure Data Center staff at the end of each day, even if the visit lasts more than one day.

During their visit, the researcher will be provided with paper on which to make notes. At the end of each day, these notes will be screened by Secure Data Center staff to ensure that no data has been copied or that no information that could be disclosive is included. After screening, the researcher can take the notes with them when they leave. Any notes not removed at the end of the visit will be securely destroyed by Secure Data Center staff.

3.4.4 Reporting considerations

The institutions involved have to agree on a reporting system for use of the access points. A meeting to discuss details is scheduled for May 2022, before the Safe Rooms are open to international researchers.

3.5 Communication

To facilitate access to international controlled data via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access, it is vital to ensure all necessary information is easily accessible and where it is needed, in the first instance online, but more will be needed by the researcher later in the process in the Trusted Research Environment itself (User Guide) and in the Safe Room (login instructions).

3.5.1 Access guide

At the UK Data Service, a special guide⁴¹ ‘UKDS SecureLab: access to non-ONS data for researchers outside of the UK via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access’ has been produced and made available online.⁴²

At the Secure Data Centre at GESIS a similar guide will be produced as part of the wider review of researcher guidance in anticipation of the first researchers using the remote connection.

3.5.2 Data catalogue

Ideally, the data should be findable in the data catalogue of the relevant TRE. However, changing search functionalities takes time and resources, as it will involve changing and setting up new filters as well as programmers’ time.

The UK Data Service as well as the Secure Data Centre at GESIS are working on implementing these data catalogue changes. In the meantime, the relevant information will be provided on their respective websites.

3.5.3 Trusted Researcher Environment guide

The SecureLab User Guide⁴³ is made available prior to accessing the SecureLab and is also available in the UKDS SecureLab environment.

Researchers working in the Secure Data Center at GESIS are provided with User Guidance documents prior to their first visit to the Safe Room.

⁴¹ UK Data Service 2022e

⁴² UK Data Service: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/find-data/access-conditions/secure-application-requirements/apply-to-access-non-ons-data-outside-uk/>; [Accessed April 11, 2022b]

⁴³ UK Data Service 2022d

3.5.4 Safe Room instructions

Users of both Safe Rooms will receive instructions regarding login procedure, working in the Secure Data Facility, and on how to request outputs.

Researchers working in the Secure Data Center at GESIS are provided with User Guidance documents prior to their first visit to the Safe Room. These documents include the rules of working within the Safe Room,⁴⁴ a guide to the virtual environment,⁴⁵ and instructions on producing research outputs.

Currently, UKDS and GESIS are working on producing relevant A4 size leaflets to be displayed in the Safe Rooms for researchers' convenience.

4. Technical and Researcher tests

Once the Secure Remote Connections between the two TREs was contractually, technically, data permission wise, and procedurally setup, two technical tests were performed in January 2022 followed by a researcher testing both ways on 1 April 2022. This has proven to be very useful as it enabled the detection of some technical issues which could then be successfully resolved.

4.1 Technical tests

The GESIS Thin Client was received by UKDS staff and displayed a local logon screen when switched on. It was tested with GESIS' support to confirm functionality. An issue was identified with the Google DNS settings no longer allowed and adjusted with Essex DNS Servers, changes were then confirmed with GESIS staff through the management portal and made permanent. An issue with launching a stable remote desktop connection was caused by outgoing traffic filtering. However, additional ports were requested and allowed from the Thin Client IP address. A second test confirmed all is working well (without any access to secure data during both tests).

The UKDS Thin Client was received at GESIS, and the local fixed IP address set collaboratively by the UKDA and GESIS IT teams. The GESIS' IP address was whitelisted on the UKDA firewall and access to the Login page was confirmed. Issues were encountered with the keyboard layout which was set to ISO

⁴⁴ GESIS 2020

⁴⁵ Kampann 2022

keyboards where an ANSI keyboard was used. The setup was quickly resolved by the UKDS IT team and GESIS staff.

4.2 Researcher tests

Researcher Tests took place on 1 April 2022. For these tests, external researchers submitted research applications, following the full applications procedures of the relevant TRE. The researchers then carried out a short piece of analysis, using live projects and data. The tests are described in more detail in the SSHOC report “Milestone 29 Tested connections between partners with live data and researcher projects”⁴⁶.

5. Lessons learned and conclusions

The report comments on the different aspects that have to be taken into consideration ahead of and during the endeavour of setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs and, thus, provides guidance for the necessary steps along the way. The details might be different in other cases, but all the mentioned main areas of work will have to be addressed when setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two TREs.

Setting up a Secure Remote Connection between the UKDS SecureLab and The Secure Data Centre at GESIS within the SSHOC project faced multiple challenges.

Unforeseeable and unprecedented challenges came up due to the onset of the COVID-19 Pandemic in 2020. As a result, both Safe Rooms were closed in March 2020, and staff and researchers moved to working from home. Due to the long duration of the pandemic, the Safe Rooms remain closed throughout the life of the SSHOC project. This has caused considerable, lengthy, and repeated delays at all stages of the set up and testing of the remote connection. This had a profound impact on the timeframe of this deliverable and what could be achieved by the end of the SSHOC project. However, with determination, flexibility and creativity at both ends, the goals of the task were achieved: two Safe Room access points have been set up, one at the UKDS Safe Room and one at GESIS’ Safe Room, and access has been technically and researcher-tested.

What are the lessons learned along the way?

⁴⁶ Wiltshire, Voronin, and Lichtwardt forthcoming

1. For international collaborations on accessing controlled data across borders *the concept of equivalence is needed to deal with some of the differences between the national implementations of data protection*. There is no guarantee that our implementation of equivalence will be valid in any bilateral agreement between a data controller and a data service provider. However, the conceptual agreement works in principle between the UK and Germany, and between Germany and the UK.
2. Different data depositors have different levels of risk-averseness. It is helpful to be able to *demonstrate not only the access conditions and application procedures, but also the respective Licence Compliance Policies* of the international partners.
3. *Remote set up of the Thin Clients vs. configuring Thin Clients before sending*. For the GESIS Thin Client, UKDS colleagues were able to make changes. These changes were not permanent before the remote end at GESIS went to the management console and accepted the changes the partner institution was proposing. This has proven to be a good idea and a good way of handling it. As it has still to be confirmed/validated by the institution where the data are held (Party A), the Thin Client owner is still controlling the Thin Client.
4. *Shipping the Thin Clients* from the UK to Germany and the other way around was quite an endeavour. This had its causes in new regulations following Brexit and difficulties caused by delays due to the COVID-19 Pandemic situation. *It might be possible to explore other options* of getting Thin Clients into place in both locations.
5. Further, there are a variety of *security changes that happen within institutions*. These have to be anticipated and need to be taken into account.
6. *A recommendation is to have a trusted technical administrator situated at the remote location*. This administrator can then manage and maintain the Thin Client on the data supplier's behalf. Even if the need to ship and swap a replacement occurred, the approved technical administrator would be able to make adjustments to the Thin Client replacement. This saves time and costs.
8. Researchers need *clear instructions on how to apply for the relevant datasets*. Specifics, for example, if one institution does not provide complete datasets but produces tailor-made datasets according to the variables specified in the project application, this needs to be clearly communicated - online or via guidelines alongside the application forms.
9. A type of *Safe Researcher Training should be part of the application* process for accessing secure data. It is vital for teaching researchers how to safely use the TRE without risking procedural breaches and vital for researchers to be aware of Statistical Disclosure Control, and thus ideally placing them in a position to only request outputs that should be releasable.

10. A laminated A4 *guide in the respective Safe Room* on how to login using the Thin Client, access the data, manoeuvre in the Secure Environment, as well as request outputs is a must-have for Safe Room Remote Desktop Access.

11. *In addition to the technical testing of the Safe Room remote desktop access, recommendation is to collect feedback from researchers testing the connection* when starting their projects - both ways. This provides useful feedback and highlights opportunities for improvements to make the researcher experience as smooth and pleasant as it can be.

Despite all the above-mentioned hurdles along the way, through the collaborative work undertaken within the SSHOC Deliverable D5.11, for the first time, controlled GESIS data will be made available to researchers outside of Germany, via the GESIS access point at the UK Data Service Safe Room at the UKDA, University of Essex. This is a major achievement within a comparably short time, and within an unprecedented time of great disruption due to the global pandemic. Further, 43 controlled longitudinal UKDS SecureLab data will now also be available via the Secure Data Centre at GESIS Safe Room.

This is another step in the direction of improving the international secure data infrastructure to facilitate evidence-based, global, policy-relevant, impactful research.

Although the COVID-19 Pandemic is not entirely over yet, a staggered return to the offices and Safe Room openings are in sight and so, even though the SSHOC project itself comes to an end at the end of April 2022, work on and around the access points, generating use cases, improving workflows etc. will continue.

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7. Appendix

Appendix 1: Controlled data the UK Data Service makes available via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access at international UKDS SecureLab access points

British Household Panel Survey⁴⁷

[6340 British Household Panel Survey, Waves 1-18, 1991-2009: Secure Access, National Grid Reference \(Easting, Northing, OSGRDIND\)](#)

Understanding Society⁴⁸

[6676 Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2019 and Harmonised BHPS: Waves 1-18, 1991-2009: Secure Access](#)

[7332 Understanding Society: Innovation Panel, Waves 1-13, 2008-2020: Secure Access, National Grid Reference \(Easting, Northing, OSGRDIND\)](#)

Millennium Cohort Study⁴⁹

[8756 Millennium Cohort Study, Sweeps 1-7, 2001-2019: Exact Participation Dates: Secure Access](#)

[8755 Millennium Cohort Study, Sweeps 1-7, 2001-2019: Demographics, Language and Religion: Secure Access](#)

[8754 Millennium Cohort Study, Sweeps 1-7, 2001-2019: Self-Reported Health, Behaviour and Fertility: Secure Access](#)

[8753 Millennium Cohort Study, Sweeps 1-7, 2001-2019: Socio-Economic, Accommodation and Occupational Data: Secure Access](#)

[8759 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Seventh Survey, 2011 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[8758 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Seventh Survey, 2001 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[8757 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Seventh Survey: Secure Access](#)

[8232 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Sixth Survey, 2011 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[8231 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Sixth Survey, 2001 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[7763 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Fifth Survey, 2011 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[7762 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Fifth Survey, 2001 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

[7761 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Fourth Survey: Secure Access](#)

[7760 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Third Survey: Secure Access](#)

[7759 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, Second Survey: Secure Access](#)

[7758 Millennium Cohort Study: Geographical Identifiers, First Survey: Secure Access](#)

⁴⁷ [British Household Panel Survey](#)

⁴⁸ [Understanding Society](#)

⁴⁹ [Millennium Cohort Study](#)

1970 British Cohort Study⁵⁰

- [8787 1970 British Cohort Study: Activity Histories, 1986-2016: Secure Access](#)
- [8555 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 46, Sweep 10 Geographical Identifiers, 2016-2018: Secure Access](#)
- [8213 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 26, Sweep 5 Geographical Identifiers, 1996: Secure Access](#)
- [8212 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 16, Sweep 4 Geographical Identifiers, 1986: Secure Access](#)
- [8211 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 10, Sweep 3 Geographical Identifiers, 1980: Secure Access](#)
- [8115 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 42, Sweep 9, Geographical Identifiers, 2011 Census Boundaries, 2012: Secure Access](#)
- [8114 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 42, Sweep 9 Geographical Identifiers, 2001 Census Boundaries, 2012: Secure Access](#)
- [8113 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 38, Sweep 8 Geographical Identifiers, 2008-2009: Secure Access](#)
- [8112 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 34, Sweep 7 Geographical Identifiers, 2004-2005: Secure Access](#)
- [8111 1970 British Cohort Study: Age 29, Sweep 6 Geographical Identifiers, 1999-2000: Secure Access](#)
- [8084 1970 British Cohort Study: Sweeps 3-9, 1980-2012, Townsend Index \(LSOA\) Linked Data: Secure Access](#)

Next Steps⁵¹

- [8656 Next Steps: Sweeps 1-8, 2004-2016: Secure Access](#)
- [8190 Next Steps: Sweep 8, 2016: Geographical Identifiers, 2011 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)
- [8189 Next Steps: Sweeps 1 and 8, 2001 and 2016: Geographical Identifiers, 2001 Census Boundaries: Secure Access](#)

National Child Development Study⁵²

- [8704 National Child Development Study: Local Authority Data, 1958-1974: Secure Access](#)
- [8221 National Child Development Study: Age 33, Sweep 5 Geographical Identifiers, 1991: Secure Access](#)
- [8220 National Child Development Study: Age 23, Sweep 4 Geographical Identifiers, 1981: Secure Access](#)
- [8219 National Child Development Study: Age 16, Sweep 3 Geographical Identifiers, 1981 Census Boundaries, 1974: Secure Access](#)
- [8218 National Child Development Study: Age 16, Sweep 3 Geographical Identifiers, 1971 Census Boundaries, 1974: Secure Access](#)
- [8085 National Child Development Study: Sweeps 3-9, 1974-2013, Townsend Index \(LSOA\) Linked Data: Secure Access](#)
- [7869 National Child Development Study: Age 55, Sweep 9 Geographical Identifiers, 2011 Census Boundaries, 2013-2014: Secure Access](#)
- [7868 National Child Development Study: Age 55, Sweep 9 Geographical Identifiers, 2001 Census Boundaries, 2013-2014: Secure Access](#)
- [7867 National Child Development Study: Age 50, Sweep 8 Geographical Identifiers, 2008-2009: Secure Access](#)
- [7866 National Child Development Study: Age 46, Sweep 7 Geographical Identifiers, 2004-2005: Secure Access](#)
- [7846 National Child Development Study: Age 42, Sweep 6 Geographical Identifiers, 1999-2000: Secure Access](#)

⁵⁰ [1970 British Cohort Study](#)

⁵¹ [Next Steps](#)

⁵² [National Child Development Study](#)

Appendix 2: Controlled data The Secure Data Centre at GESIS holds

[ALLBUS/GGSS \(Allgemeine Bevölkerungsumfrage der Sozialwissenschaften/German General Social Survey\) - Sensitive Regional Data](#)

[GLES Sensitive Regional Data](#)

[German General Social Survey ALLBUS - Small-scale Geodata 2014, 2016 and 2018](#)

[Kinship and Social Security \(KASS\)](#)

[euandi 2014 \(Expert Interviews\) - Correspondence](#)

[Universities and Technical Colleges in a System of Innovation - a Germany-wide View](#)

[Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies \(PIAAC\), Germany - Extended Version – Regional Data](#)

[Diversity and Contact](#)

[Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies \(PIAAC\), Germany - Extended Version – microm data](#)

[Europe in Context - Full Version](#)

[iFQ Survey of Scientists 2010 - full version](#)

[COCOPS Executive Survey on Public Sector Reform in Europe – Views and Experiences from Senior Executives - Full Version](#)

[MESARAS 2013: Mobility, Expectations, Self-Assessment and Risk Attitude of Students - full version](#)

[Jena Study on Social Change and Human Development \(Adults\) 2008](#)

[Jena Study on Social Change and Human Development \(Adults\) 2007](#)

[Jena Study on Social Change and Human Development \(Adults\) 2005 - Full Version](#)

[Jena Study on Social Change and Human Development \(Adults\) 2009](#)

[The Integration of the European Second Generation in Frankfurt and Berlin \(TIES Germany\) - full version](#)

[Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries \(CILS4EU\) - Full version. Data file for on-site use](#)

[Children of Immigrants Longitudinal Survey in Four European Countries - Germany \(CILS4EU-DE\) - Full version. Data file for on-site use](#)

[GESIS Panel - Extended Edition](#)

Appendix 3: UKDS data collections by access level

Data access conditions	Access level
Open Licence	Open
End User Licence (EUL) [Authentication]	Safeguarded
Special Conditions (SC) [Authentication]	
Special Licence (SL) [Authentication, Accredited Researcher Status]	
<u>SecureLab</u> Data Access (remote) [Authentication, Accredited Researcher Status, Training + Test]	Controlled
<u>SecureLab</u> Data Safe Room Access (on-site) [Authentication, Accredited Researcher Status, Training + Test]	

